

Two rice hybrids released in Andhra Pradesh, India

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Since 1988, we have been working to develop rice hybrids by using effective local restorer lines. The five top performers (MTU HR 2000, MTU HR 2001, MTU HR 2002, MTU HR 2003, and MTU HR 2008) were tested in farmers' fields throughout Andhra Pradesh, India, during the 1992 and 1993 wet seasons.

Each hybrid was grown in a 500-1000-m² plot along with a popular local cultivar as a check. Plants were transplanted at 1-2 seedlings hill⁻¹, at a population of 40-45 hills m⁻². Local cultural practices were followed.

Of the five hybrids, MTU HR 2003 and MTU HR 2008 performed exceedingly well across locations (see table).

In 1992, MTU HR 2003 produced a 1.1 t ha⁻¹ mean yield advantage over the best check (4.8 t ha⁻¹) across 11 locations. In 1993, it produced a 1.3 t ha⁻¹ mean yield advantage over the best check (5.8 t ha⁻¹) in six out of seven districts.

MTU HR 2008 performed well at three locations during 1992, with a mean yield advantage of more than 3 t ha⁻¹ over the check. During 1993, the same hybrid outperformed the best check (5.7 t ha⁻¹) with a mean yield advantage of 1.3 t ha⁻¹. The hybrid produced maximum yields of 10-11 t ha⁻¹.

The Andhra Pradesh Agricultural University released MTU HR 2003 as APHR 1 and MTU HR 2008 as APHR 2 in December 1993. APHR 1 (IR58025 A/Vajram R) is a medium-duration (130-135 d) hybrid, while APHR 2 (IR62829 A / MTU 9992 R) is short in duration (120 d). Both are tolerant of lodging, intermediate in height, and have long slender grains with good cooking quality. APHR 2 performs well under low inputs and possesses tolerance for bacterial leaf blight. ■

Mean yield performance of MTU HR 2003 (APHR-1) and MTU HR 2008 (APHR-2) in minikit trials. Andhra Pradesh, India. 1992 and 1993 wet seasons.

District	Locations (no.)	Mean yield of hybrid (t ha ⁻¹)	Mean yield of best check (t ha ⁻¹)	Yield advantage over the best check (t ha ⁻¹)
<i>MTU HR 2003 (1992 wet season)</i>				
Warangal	3	7.0	6.2	0.8
Ranga Reddy	2	3.6	2.8	0.9
Kurnool	2	7.8	6.4	1.3
Chittoor	1	7.5	6.0	1.5
East Godavari	2	4.1	3.7	0.4
West Godavari	1	5.3	4.0	1.4
Mean	11	5.9	4.8	1.1
<i>MTU HR 2003 (1993 wet season)</i>				
Nalgonda	2	9.3	6.6	2.7
Ranga Reddy	3	6.3	5.2	1.0
Waragal	3	7.5	6.1	1.4
Kurnool	5	8.1	7.0	1.0
Krishna	5	7.3	5.4	1.9
Guntur	1	5.5	3.9	1.5
West Godavari	3	4.7	4.8	-0.2
Mean	22	7.1	5.8	1.3
<i>MTU HR 2008 (1992 wet season)</i>				
Ranga Reddy	1	10.0	6.5	3.5
Krishna	1	9.4	6.6	2.8
Anantapur	1	10.4	7.5	2.9
Mean	3	9.9	6.9	3.1
<i>MTU JHR 2008 (1993 wet season)</i>				
Nalgonda	2	11.0	6.6	4.4
Ranga Reddy	3	6.4	5.7	1.2
Warangal	3	6.8	5.4	1.4
Kurnool	6	8.1	6.9	1.2
Krishna	6	6.8	5.2	1.5
Guntur	3	6.3	5.9	0.4
West Godavari	4	5.3	4.8	0.5
Mean	27	7.1	6.7	1.3

Performance of hybrid rice in irrigated lowlands, Uttar Pradesh, India

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In the Tarai region of northwestern India, irrigated rice yields are high, with many farmers harvesting 7 t ha⁻¹ or more. Hybrid rice varieties, with their higher yield potential, should have a place in these areas.

We evaluated the performance of newly developed hybrid PRH-1 (PMS2A/IR31802) compared with that of high-yielding inbred varieties (Jaya,

Yields of hybrid PRH-1 (PMS 2A/IR31802) and high-yielding inbred rice varieties at two N rates. Pantnagar, India, 1994-95 wet seasons.

Treatment	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)		
	1994	1995	Mean
N rate (kg ha ⁻¹)			
120	6.4	6.3	6.4
160	7.0	6.6	6.8
SE±	0.1	0.1	
CD(5%)	ns	ns	
Varieties			
PRH-1	7.7	7.1	7.4
Jaya	6.7	6.4	6.5
Pant Dhan 4	6.2	-	6.2
Pant Dhan 10	-	6.0	6.0
Pant Dhan 12	6.3	6.3	6.3
SE±	0.1	0.1	
CD(5%)	0.3	0.3	
Interaction			
	ns	ns	
CV (%) based on error b	4	4	